

Review

Strategic Relations between the United States and Russia: A Review of Global Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract: This research investigates the origins, dynamics, and current state of strategic ties that have existed between the United States and Russia ever since the end of the Cold War. The paper examines the theoretical element of the topic, which is the influence of mutual internal compulsions, differing foreign policies, and decision-making procedures of both nations when they were under different Administrations. An investigation of the threats posed to the peace and order of Asia by the proliferation of nuclear weapons and to the multi-polar global order by the state of ties between the United States and Russia is carried out. The primary purpose of this research is to understand the dynamics of the strategic relationship between the United States and Russia in light of the multi-polar world and to investigate the extent to which both nations have successfully maintained a peaceful and secure world order. An analysis of the funds needed to build up Russia's strategic nuclear forces shows that spending at the same level and cutting the arsenal down to 1500 warheads will keep the country's deterrent power for the next 10–15 years. However, at this level of spending, it will not be able to change the strategic direction of the US or keep Washington interested in keeping the arms control talks going.

Keywords: Nuclear Strategy, US-Russia Strategic Relations, Neighborhood Policy, Cold War, Financial Policy.

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Introduction

Russia's opposition to US-EU and NATO policies in Syria, Iran, and Iraq and its support for the unification of Crimea and South Ossetia have made people worldwide worried about a "New Cold War." In this way, many questions arise, such as: Did the old Cold War end? Is there an alternative to this two-way conversation that wants to build a militarized world with two sides [1,2].

In this concern, it could say that the old Cold War, which was based on economic and military competition between the US and the Soviet Union, ended with the fall of the Soviet Union in 1991. But the Warsaw Pact, which the Soviet Union led, broke up, but NATO did not. Also, more countries joined NATO, including some from the old Soviet bloc. Russia is against the proactive US-NATO policy of encouraging regime change through direct military intervention, support for local civil wars, and identity nationalism, among other things. The West used this in West Asia, Central Asia, and

some former Soviet states. It was done because "rogue regimes" in Iraq, Libya, and Afghanistan threatened the West [3,4].

Asia and Africa no longer have any proxy wars. People today know about US foreign policy during the Cold War and how it affected the economies of the West and the Soviet Union. This is an important fact. The other factor is the rise of new powers like China, India, Brazil, and Indonesia, which cannot be pulled into Cold War-style politics of black and white. This is clear from the fact that they asked Russia and the European Union to talk and find a middle ground. The US defense budget has doubled since 9/11; 2001 [5,6].

The budget rate is higher than it cost to fight in the Vietnam War. At that time, Russia tested a new intercontinental ballistic missile, and many European Union countries were discussing raising their defense budgets. The world economy is going through a rough patch, and many European Union countries still have to cut back on spending. Therefore, a New Cold War will worsen things, and many European Union countries are still going through austerity. So, a New Cold War will make things worse [7,8].

At a meeting in Russia in 2009, U.S. President Barack Obama said that the U.S. needs a strong, peaceful, and wealthy Russia. Conversely, Russia needs an America that is responsible, peaceful, recognized, and active. It needs an America that builds partnerships with other countries on an equal footing and works to improve its position as new international relationships are made [9,10].

Collins, who was the U.S. ambassador to Russia in 2010, said that a weak and unpredictable Russia would cause a lot of trouble in Europe and Asia. The United States thinks that if Russia gets weaker, it could lead to unimaginable problems with getting rid of nuclear weapons, controlling strategic nuclear missiles, dealing with organized crime inside and outside Russia, and spreading pollution and diseases. Madeleine Albright, the former U.S. Secretary of State, said that "three-quarters of U.S. aid to Russia is used to reduce the nuclear threat of war and to keep weapons of mass destruction from falling into the wrong hands, which is still the U.S.'s biggest worry [11,12]."

Medvedev made an important statement in 2010: "I am glad that we were able to change the atmosphere between Russia and the United States over the past year. That does not mean we shouldn't try to find differences in our relationships. Instead, we should build a long-term relationship based on democratic values, economic freedom, and shared goals to stop global threats. We will work with the U.S. on the most important things, such as fighting terrorism, trans-border crime, and piracy. The areas that aren't a source of conflict, but the sources of conflict still exist, which means that their relationship will continue to be rocky [13,14]."

Differences in American and Soviet Thinking on Nuclear Strategy

A school of thought stated that the destructiveness of modern weapons has rendered fighting obsolete as a way of settling international issues. Other schools of thought focused on philosophical and moral problems, neglecting vital and equally significant military matters from international affairs. Once the Axis countries collapsed, the international system rapidly polarized into two antagonistic blocs, compounding the uncertainty and fear about the nuclear armament system's ramifications. As the Soviet Union started building its nuclear arsenal, political and military officials on both sides speculated about nuclear war and the implications of modern weapons on the world political order [15–17].

Hence, both nations' theoreticians developed military theories and strategies suitable for the nuclear era. "Military doctrine is a set of prescriptive principles designed to ensure "uniformity of thought and action" throughout a nation's armed forces pursuing policies during peace and war. It defines how the military should contribute to the state's political activities and how military action should be used to achieve its goals. Strategy is the wide range of military operations congruent with the doctrine utilized when implementing state policy. Military theory and tactics have traditionally mirrored each nation's intellectual and cultural atmosphere and economic, political, geographic, and social qualities. A state's political system and ideology, national aims and ambitions, historical experiences and vision, and

the world's political environment influence its doctrine and strategy. At the same time, geography and resources dictate their feasibility." Military doctrine results from a long, complicated process of official concept formulation and evolution. Military doctrine depends on the state's ruling class's political ideology and economic and moral resources.

During the Cold War of the 1950s and 1960s, the U.S. had more and better nuclear weapons than the S.U., which was obsessed with dealing with the U.S. U.S. doctrine and strategy changed with nuclear capability balances. "The U.S. avoided utilizing restricted military measures in opposition to Soviet political and Military operations across the globe and instead threatened the Soviet Union with nuclear assault for any of an indefinite list of military and Political actions" under enormous reprisal [18].

The idea of mutually assured destruction, which held that as long as either side could inflict harm on the other, neither side would have the motivation to start a nuclear war, underpinned the U.S. policy of deterrence to avoid large-scale nuclear conflict. Mutually assured destruction became the U.S. deterrence paradigm, sparking a never-ending debate over military force size and kind. Mutually assured destruction was divisive. One group advocated a forced "balance" between sides. The other claims that to discourage a future invader, one needs just enough military might guarantee the aggressor that a nuclear exchange would hurt both sides. Regardless of Soviet and Chinese force builds, proponents have increasingly used "sufficiency" to justify decreasing U.S. nuclear force levels. The US did not shift away from the guaranteed destruction idea and add escalation control and war survival in its doctrine and strategy until former Secretary of Defense James R. Schlesinger rethought American policy. Hence, mutually assured annihilation deters nuclear conflict, the strategy's core objective. The current theory is that nuclear war may be hard to manage and may escalate quickly, but it is not automatic. Lastly, it commits to enhancing American military, political, and economic might compared to the adversary if escalation cannot be prevented [19].

Hence, American ideas sought to ensure US survival or reduce war damage. American nuclear warfare speculation has never been popular. Herman Kahn's early 1960s "Thermonuclear war and thinking about the inconceivable" was met with theoretical objections. It showed how unfathomable the issue was for American academics, politicians, and the public. Nuclear conflict can be won, according to James Sch Lesinger. Several military thinkers and students at professional military colleges have pondered surviving and winning different sorts of nuclear warfare, although American policy has seldom used them. US strategists say Dynamic and democratic processes shape American policy, doctrine, and strategy. The US posture will depend on its political leadership, national and international events, and military and civilian strategic strategists. Soviet nuclear philosophy and strategy were fundamentally different from U.S. Soviet military theory and strategy aim to prevent a nuclear war. But, Soviet doctrine and strategy reflect the fundamental disparities between Soviet and American political systems, ideologies, historical experiences, geographic locations, economic and technological capabilities, and conceptions of themselves and the world. The Soviet approach to military theory and strategy differs greatly from the West's. The Soviets highlighted their ideological commitment to changing the existing quo, whereas the Americans have sought to retain the current international order. They see international politics as dynamic [20].

Soviet military literature has qualities that U.S. military literature lacks. (1) The Soviet argument that Marxist and Leninism, the foundation for social phenomena, underpins Soviet military conceptions. Under Marshall V.D. Sokolovsky's Military volume strategy (1960), military doctrine is a class phenomenon rooted in society's economic realities. History shapes military doctrine. The state ruling class's political line and economic and moral resources determine military doctrine. The U.S. believed the Soviets believed there were no universal policies for strategic stability, creation, and official identity expansion. Russians never sought to define such a program. Soviet military specialists doubt that doctrine can be established cognitively or that any doctrine can apply to all countries, plans, and tactics. Military philosophy establishes S.U. values, whereas military strategy covers military force deployment before and during the battle [21].

Soviet notions that doctrine cannot be formed by a purposeful academic method limit debate of alternative theories and their merits. The U.S. says that Soviet strategy and tactics publications do not promote academic debate. To achieve state political goals, determine the best military ideas and methods. Marxism-Leninism is socio-political and does not guide Soviet military strategy and tactics. It creates armed troops and politically acceptable warfare. The Soviet authorities' policies, interpretations, and actions were based on Marxism [22].

The Soviets saw war as class warfare. Soviet officials claimed that the communist state was peaceful and would never start a war. It is ready to fight capitalist-imperialist countries. The class struggle also makes the capitalist side want to destroy the socialist camp. Consequently, a strong peacetime deterrent was needed. In battle, the ideological imperative requires "destruction of the enemy's military forces, "the invasion and holding of the land, and "everlasting vigilance" in the security of Soviet territory against invasion [23]."

A country must have superior troops to have such a capacity. Soviet officials think that military power determines peacetime rights. Soviet officials want a military force to protect their foreign policy from outside intervention. Also, the 1962 Cuban missile crisis taught the Soviets about themselves. It accelerated Soviet armaments building. The country may accept a military power's ultimatum. Assured annihilation, enormous reprisal, and balance of terror were debated as national strategic possibilities. The possibility of a US war-winning or survival capacity is recognized as equally important in this setting. American nuclear deterrence drives historical preoccupation. It continues to discourage debate of nuclear war policy measures that might protect the US [24].

In his 1971 monograph, Marshall A.A. Grechiko defended Soviet military achievements in Soviet terms. No social groupings in the USSR or other socialist states wanted war, and they couldn't. During the 24th Congress, L.I. Brezhnev remarked, "We have territorial claims on no one whatsoever. All people should grow freely and independently. Nevertheless, don't threaten the US. 71 Soviet nuclear tactics are two-fold. The first requires a military force that can dissuade prospective foes from using nuclear weapons during peacetime and survive and beat the adversary in wartime. Second, a strong military to deter other states, even nuclear powers, from restricting Soviet peacetime prerogatives by force or threat of force [25].

Soviet theorists studied various theoretical concerns, from aiming nuclear weapons to transporting the army through nuclear strike zones. The USSR, which was protected by two seas, had a very different worldview than the US. Before intercontinental bombers and missiles, the US mainly depended on the navy to defend against invasion. The US prepared for a ground invasion and fought both of its major wars on home soil. The Soviets were more concerned about a full-scale invasion after a large nuclear assault on her military bases and centers of government, industry, and people than scholarly conjecture. The S.U. has also confronted more possible opponents across the oceans and on her frontiers. Hence, Soviet policy in the nuclear age and before had to adapt to a more extensive range of threats and conflict scenarios. Soviet plans recommended a combined conventional and nuclear force superior to any prospective opponent or probable enemy combination to deter attacks. Marshal Grechko said on Soviet military strategy: To be fully prepared for future battle, it is vital to consistently follow Lenin's theory that the winning side would dominate economic, scientific, technological, socio-political, moral, and military fields. The army's socio-political, economic, and military capacities demonstrate this dominance [26].

The Soviet policy requires nuclear and military superiority and a robust standing army. As soviet leaders have remarked, such a force not only deters aggression but also allows politics to accomplish its goals. Soviet strategy varies from U.S. strategy because it views nuclear warfare differently. In a nuclear confrontation, ground forces are essential to the Russians. U.S. nuclear warfare has featured a convulsive or spasmodic exchange of weapons, leaving both states prostrate and unable to organize invasion troops and land armies. The U.S. and Soviet danger includes the risk of a nuclear conflict between themselves and peripheral Euro-Asian states. The Soviet strategy also calls for maintaining large standing armies that are highly mobile, have great firepower, and can seize the initiative and achieve large territorial gains in the ground war before, during, and after exchanging long-range weapons. Russians believe nuclear

weapons do not affect the war. The offensive analyses Clausewitz's view of 20th-century warfare's rising ferocity and devastation. Nuclear weapons advanced mass devastation. Sidorenko said that both tactically and strategically, nuclear weapons have minimized the difference between the enemy's front and rear lines and given the attacker the capacity to rapidly and decisively penetrate enormous regions of the enemy's positional defenses. Modern large-scale ground combat is more about maneuver and initiative than attrition [27].

The following remark that a nuclear war will be substantially more catastrophic than any previous conflict is an essential corollary to this belief. Instead of utilizing conventional bombers to target enemy cities as in the previous war, ballistic missiles will be used. Instead of long-range artillery and conventional air support on the battlefield, armies will use nuclear artillery and jet aircraft carrying tactical nuclear weapons. The Soviets believed World War-III would be worse than World War Two. For political decision-making and diplomatic exchange, nuclear forces are constrained if achieving specific political/military goals demands preserving economic and military resources and Government/population centers. That implies both nations' strategies embrace the later agreements and obligations, which affect their strategic and tactical combat. It believes nuclear and conventional weapons are necessary for national security and other goals in war and peace [28].

The twenty-fourth Soviet Communist Party Congress "sought to contribute to the restoration of ties and to rebuild goodwill with the Chinese People's Republic." But, CPSU never concedes to Soviet national interests or Marxism-Leninism." The S.U.'s animosity towards her Eastern European satellites makes a multilateral conflict more likely. The threat of keeping her friends' revolutionaries at bay after a nuclear assault or while fighting on another front motivates the U.S. to retain her enormous forward-based standing army and a nuclear umbrella against foreign nuclear powers friendly to Eastern Europe. It also reaffirms the U.S. and Russia's strategic relevance in this alliance, which aligns with their national interests. The strategic connection between the two nations during the Cold War should be used to analyze nuclear war deterrence and prosecution objectively [29].

Conflict in Myanmar

Conflict prevention still seems an alien concept in Myanmar. The political class or the governments do not bother to take cognizance of a problem until that spirals into violent clashes resulting in the loss of precious human lives. There are many examples from the region whereby violence could have been averted had there been swift action from the ruling government [16].

In Myanmar, the ruling government is running a campaign against the Rohingya Muslims to exterminate them from their country. Rohingya are the stateless people in Myanmar's Rakhine province. Myanmar refuses to recognize them as citizens. The ethnic group has been under repression by the government since the 1970s. In the latest crisis, the government has launched an "ethnic cleansing" campaign as per a UN official. Myanmar refrains from recognizing Rohingya as citizens because accepting them as legal citizens will eventually bestow all the constitutional rights and privileges to the ethnic community. The Myanmar government is always sticking to its usual practice of systematically denying the rights to the community [17].

The culture of post-crisis response is deeply embedded in the governance structure of South Asian countries. Several factors hamper the actions of the ruling government. One of the significant factors is the lack of political will of the governments to act in times of crisis. It is almost a common feature in every country in South Asia. Had there been solid political will against the masses or religious leaders stoking communal violence, several of the violent clashes in the past between different communities could have been averted [18].

US-Russia Strategic Relations

The rebalancing of American power and Russia's aggressive conduct in Europe's security environment affect the EU's position, while the US's readiness to participate as a security provider signals a more active engagement in European

disputes. This American "Role" is also conditioned by the need to manage ties with a Russia that regards itself as equal only to the US. Complex equations pose problems regarding the EU as International Strategic Actor [30].

International relations have seen regime changes, re-adjustment, and remarkable alterations in the strategic environment. Once the Cold War ended, the world and Russia confronted two mutually existent developments. First, the economic and political powers of many nation-states and their integrative ties, as well as national ones, would build a better multilateral governance framework for international institutions and processes. The second tendency is to inherit and defend an international framework based on considerable domination by the industrialized West under American supremacy and prone to seek unilateral solutions, notably by using military might address key international issues [31].

After 11 September 2001, the Treaty of Maastricht was attacked for its flaws, highlighting the EU's role in international affairs. In this context, two key essential concerns were raised: whether European foreign policy revealed its limitations and highlighted defects or whether, via re-nationalization, member states intended to rectify the gaps and weaknesses of the collective system. In U.S.-Russia and EU strategic relations, Iraq-Afghanistan, Kashmir, Israel-Palestine and ESDP are major issues [32]. Before examining the EU's relationship with the US and Russia, it is vital to understand its foreign policy, coherence principle, and contemporary issues [33].

Following the collapse of the Maastricht Treaty creating a Constitution for Europe and a "period of reflection," the Lisbon summit adopted a "Reform Treaty" on October 19, 2007, which took effect on December 1, 2009. These might improve European foreign policy and enhance the EU as an international force. Coherence is essential for EU foreign policy and all international players. Coherence formerly challenged European foreign policy. So, the EU's structure and institutional engagement and processes in several foreign policy problem areas. The EU's structure and legal identity have been cited as obstacles to its foreign policy and international standing. Yet, the European Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) and the national actions of Member States like the US and Russia have differed. Since the Treaty of Maastricht established the European Union, the Treaty on European Union has defined the idea of coherence in foreign relations (TEU). Article 3 of the Treaty on European Union in its consolidated form of Nice (2002)/ TEU (N) states that the Union "must, in particular, preserve the coherence of its exterior actions as a whole in the framework of its external relations, security, economic and development policies." Hence, the Article coordinates and coheres to "external actions as a whole" and ensures uniformity across all EU external connections. This clause relates to the degree of internal coordination of EU policies and suggests that EU foreign policies should converge or at least not conflict. The Council and Commission must "maintain such uniformity and shall work to this aim." Therefore, the EU's exterior efforts must be coherent to "establish its identity on the world landscape [34]."

Al Qaeda solved America's most significant problems! It shows fundamentalist enmity and Western fragility. Israel-Palestine tensions are rising. The EU faces four main challenges: 1) the war in Afghanistan, 2) the "war on terrorism,"; and 3) the possibility of an American/Western assault on Iraq. The EU's instant response to New York and Washington's horrific photos. Notwithstanding Western European anti-Americanism and Bush administration animosity. NATO nations used Article V of the Treaty to help the US if the assaults were foreign-directed (by October 2, this was thought proven, and the commitment was declared operational) [35].

Pre-9/11 foreign policy issues have persisted in the EU and Member States despite popular awareness. The Middle East crises, Kashmir, expanded American unilateralism, and the "new foreign policy agenda" will be my focus (drugs, illegal immigration, and national building) [36].

American inactivity allowed Israel to dominate the EU's constructive diplomacy. In May, the Quartet—the US, Russia, the UN, and the EU—promoted talks between key parties, giving Europeans a significant role in peacemaking. Moratinos and Solana may build [37].

But, the EU required three Quartet representatives (Solana, Patten, and the Presidency). This is hardly convincing given that Israel damaged Palestinian Authority facilities funded by massive EU financing and prevented Solana and the Spanish President from visiting Yasser Arafat. Another international gesture is the Quartet [38].

Cynically, providing the EU and Russia a cosmetic interest in US-sponsored mediation may keep them compromised. In May, the US deemed the Europeans useful for "cleaning up," with Italy intending to expatriate the Palestinians without consultation [39].

Western Europe harshly denounced Israel, blaming Sharon for the region's daily killing. Spain, France, and Belgium demanded EU sanctions on Israel. Yet, cautious or pro-US nations like the UK and the Netherlands have prevented this and any EU unity. European foreign policy is stuck and silent on other big issues like Iraq. It misrepresents European opinion and risks being identified with the US and Israel by Arab allies. Since 1970, the EU has supported the Middle East peace process, and the Danish President has finished another fruitless shuttle diplomacy tour [40].

Kashmir, where Indo-Pakistani tensions loomed. EU engagement is doubtful. Britain's historical links to both parties and dedication to global peacemaking led the Union to crisis diplomacy. Pakistan became a major European problem when Al Qaeda entered Afghanistan. Human rights and nuclear proliferation have delayed the Third Generation Cooperation Agreement since 1996. Trade and financing were allowed. Europe needed General Musharraf's aid [41].

As 2002 progressed, Kashmir and nuclear weapons issues were increasingly linked. Musharraf wanted to use his new influence with the West to push India, which had long accused Pakistan of sponsoring terrorism in Afghanistan and Kashmir and tried to avoid his issues. The EU was involved with mere carrots. Consequently, the communiqué after the third EU-India summit on October 10, 2002, did not reference Kashmir as a sensitive domestic subject. Instead, it lauded "India and the EU, global participants in a multipolar world [42]."

Realpolitik has limitations, and the European system generated different diplomatic outcomes. The EU has struggled since September 11, 2001, due to American unilateralism. The terrorism issue began with the Bush administration. September 11, 2001, woke up a unilateralist government to the necessity for global alliances. The US has made indirect International Criminal Court concessions to secure important allies' support [43].

The Bush administration's apparent antipathy for the Johannesburg Earth Summit, which Tony Blair attended and demonstrated a personal commitment to, and the US departure from the Kyoto Agreement on greenhouse emissions have united Europeans. In commercial policy, where the common policy is stronger, European influence seems inadequate. But it can still impose steel tariffs and farm subsidies; the US has become more international. The US "hyperpower" may coerce European nations into bilateral immunity arrangements for US diplomats because of its uniqueness [44].

EU pressured US environmental policy. Conviction mingled with the awareness that European opinion strongly opposed any extensive Bush policy on GM foods. European unity on a matter where the US looks to operate differently and European interests in energy, welfare, and industry are handy. All EU nations share an international cooperation approach based on these interests and principles. The UN is the centerpiece of a Grotian international order founded on the rule of law and multilateral organizations. The fifteen "minor states" lack strong unilateralism compared to the US. Thus they cherish EU membership. Due to its unpredictability, they fear and mistrust unilateral authority. The 1930s and the US-Soviet "Brezhnev Doctrine" revised international law. As shown in Kosovo and Iraq, the US is good at coercion and divide-and-rule, whereas the Europeans vary in their loyalty to UN legitimization. However, Europeans have discovered strength in solidarity and resistance to the superpower's rogue elephant behavior [45].

Drugs and other crimes, illegal immigration, and nation-building top the new foreign policy agenda. September 11, 2001, lent legitimacy to these anti-terrorist agenda items. Transnational crime and economic refugees were neglected. Afghanistan and Lebanon struggle with warlordism due to poverty and neglect [46].

These systemic, functional/economic, long-term concerns should be addressed by the EU's "civilian power" and national competencies. The Member-States agree more easily on certain matters. They helped repair and improve numerous

failed nations financially and administratively. Afghanistan, Bosnia, Macedonia, and Sierra Leone might expand contributions swiftly [47].

The approach aims to alleviate Mediterranean migration by increasing the Maghreb and other economies. The Lome and Cotonou accords prioritized political conditionality and disadvantaged nations. Division of labor based on historical post-colonial links allows various governments to lead in different regions. These historically divergent links also mean that bilateralism can quickly replace collective diplomacy, as was the case in July 2002 when the Spanish government fell into conflict with Morocco over the disputed Islet of Perini and found itself without CFSP support, especially due to French ties to Rabat [48].

Powell's successful mediation was embarrassing for Europe. Immediate challenges may indeed delay long-term solutions. To remind the EU of its significance and contradict Greek stances on Cyprus and the ESDP, Turkey turns a blind eye to the journeys of Kurds and other refugees from its territory, undermining the EU's efforts to regulate the influx of illegal migrants in Greece and Italy's beaches [49].

Three key foreign policy concerns facing the EU. These include the ESDP, expansion, and the Constitutional Convention, which calls for institutional reforms in foreign policy. These issues are related [49].

The ESDP boomed in 1998 and is nearing its "headline target" of a 60,000-man Rapid Response Force by 2003. Its main goals were to provide the EU a limited but actual military power, notably in its territory, for peacekeeping, to abolish the Western European Union (WEU) and improve the EU-NATO alliance, and to link the UK into EU foreign and security policy to strengthen solidarity. The second is done. The WEU dissolved institutionally, not legally, and the EU was militarized [50].

EU and Russia Strategic Relationship

Pieret-Ehin and Eiki Berg examined incompatible identities in Russia-EU identity politics. They called Russia and the EU "incompatible identities" and highlighted the obstacles to synergy. However, comprehending Russia and the EU requires objectively knowing their "identity Discourse." Each holds onto its "realistic" nation-state self. As "pluralisms" and "globalisation" have weakened, nation-state forces have realized their unitarian nature, and their agents have changed their status accordingly [51–53].

- Russia is the European Union's third biggest trade partner facing the task of modernizing its energy-related economy.
- Russia is the European Union's largest neighbor; Russia remains an important world player with its seat in the UN Security Council and its acquisition of nuclear arsenal.
- Russia has refused to be included in the European neighborhood policy (ENP) but insists on a strategic partnership on equal basis.
- Russia prefers an inter-governmental great power Europe to the European Union, similar to the 19th century concept of Europe, where Russia was recognized as one of the powers with an undisputed right to defend its interests.
- Russia is poorer than the European Union, with percapita real GDP being just one third of European Union average.
- Yet Russia is a European power and it is important to realize that it has interests in both Europe and Asia.
- The European Union cannot ignore Russia. It is the third biggest trade partner and as a primary energy supplier.
- The European Union is the natural partner for Russia in an alternative pole of the United States.
- The European Union presents a new super national entity.
- European Union is evinced in its European Neighborhood policy (ENP) is a neo-medieval hub of shared identity.

Iver B. Neumann believes "the Decembrists who viewed Europe as a cultural body of states that included Russia" based on these factors. He maintained that Russia should and can develop along European lines, both politically and economically, to refurbish its Europeanist self at the expense of its exclusionary Eurasian self by sharing identities with EU member states. Since the USSR collapsed, it is geopolitical to be an "integral component of contemporary European culture." Putin passionately supports Russia's Eurocentric policy [54].

Keith C. Smith also connected "the end of Eurasia with the rebirth of Russia via a strategic relationship with the European Union and key European states." So, Russia and the EU must accept that Russians see their future in Europe even if European democracy does not fit their form of administration. Hence, the Russia-NATO council locates and justifies identity savings with a concentration on more compatible identities [55].

US. Factor and Russian Resources

As the need for effective covalent bonds between the European Union and Russia grows, the evident United States "Pull" and "Push" factors in European politics have forced anti-NATO European Union sympathizers to be poor their combined resources with those of Russia to maintain a new security environment (Roger Kanet) in the post-9/11 world of trans world terror. Russia joined an extended G-8 after signing the Russia-NATO foundation agreement on May 27, 1997 [56].

Contuse the "reset" of US-Russia ties. American strategy in Iran, Afghanistan, and other conflicts was "reset" by a new weapons limitation pact and Russian assistance. The arrangement was altered because Russia, the EU, and the US coordinated their political position toward Russia. Therefore, Russia abandoned futile attempts to challenge the US's worldwide supremacy and prioritized the well-being of ethnic Russians residing outside the Russian Federation on former Soviet territory. Russia must reinvent and restore Russian identities through CSCE and the Council of Europe. Russians abroad are multipolar integrationists under international law. Thus, Russia abandoned isolationism. President Dmitri Medvedev correctly said, "Russia does not seek conflict with any nation. Russia has no aim of isolating itself. We will cultivate as much as possible positive ties with Europe, the US, and other countries of the world [57]."

Notwithstanding its "rich capacities," Russia normalized relations with the West. Russia left the realm of uro-sans mutual tolerance to form an "axis of conveniences" (Bobo Lo, 2008)⁴⁹ with the EU. Consequently, Russia rejected "national identity" and did not consider the EU a threat. Russia sought a "harmonious partnership" with the EU, arguing that international forces shape identities (Martha Finnemore: 1996:128). Russia has advocated for the EU's shared economic space and "partnership for modernization" despite its "protected sphere of interest" to promote Eurasianism [58].

European Union-United States America Strategic Relations

Since the Cold War, the European Union and the United States have had trouble getting along because they have different ideas. But this kind of split does not work in a polycentric world, which differs from a bipolar world order. The Euro-American alliance must be built up one issue at a time and then renewed at a particular time. There are many problems in the world. These range from economic growth to climate change, from the spread of nuclear weapons to peace in the region. Therefore, the EU and the US must figure out their specific areas of shared interest, look into them in-depth, and then act on them [59].

At the EU-Washington Forum in 2010, the EUISS tried to set an agenda based on the four most important internal and external problems facing Europe and the United States. Here's what they are [60-62]:

- The economic relation.
- The Middle East peace process: EU-US cooperation.
- Disarmament and non-proliferation: the road to global zero.

The EU and US share most of these viewpoints. F. Stephen Larrabee's chapter in this collection discusses how to handle Europe's unresolved repercussions from the 1989 wave of democratic revolutions in Eastern Europe and current difficulties in the EU's eastern region. Europe is not yet democratic and unified, and its eastern neighbor has hazardous war zones. Europeans have always applauded the US commitment to a free and unified Europe when the Berlin Wall fell. The US has advocated European integration in the Balkans as the best way to consolidate weak democracies, but nationalistic and extremist impulses have made this process slow and difficult. Notwithstanding their amazement at European divides over Kosovo, the US maintains this commitment. President Obama's 2010 "reset" of ties with Russia was seen as a step towards easing Georgia's tensions [63].

In the Middle East, resolving the Palestinian crisis is a shared Euro-American goal that requires robust Washington-Brussels cooperation. In recent years, this convergence has hurt the peace effort. The Americans have revived the fantasy of long-term bilateral discussions and adopted the failed European policy of constructing a Palestinian state from the bottom up. Iran's nuclear program is the US and EU's other Middle East problem. Iran's reluctance to reciprocate Obama's early initiative has made engagement with the Islamic Republic difficult. According to Bassma Kodmani, 'coercion rather than negotiation has been the prevailing tactic for dealing with Iran and it has had some results if compared against the military option.' The West has sanctioned Iran for years. The economy is another American issue. Employment may lead to the economic policy during the global slump. According to Maria JoSo Rodrigues, Europeans and Americans need a long-term plan based on a new growth model inspired by the key premise of "innovation for sustainable development." The EU and the US must engage with other global economic players like China, India, Brazil, and Japan to achieve this in a globalized and multipolar world [64].

The EU's Eastern and Western Neighborhood Policy

Eastern Europe comprises Ukraine, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Moldova, and Belarus. The US and EU want to expand democratic stability and security in this area. As Daniel Hamilton and Nikolas Foster have noted, failing to address the region's issues risks destabilizing competition and confrontation among its regional and external actors, leading to festering separatist conflicts, greater international challenges, and dysfunctional energy markets, which could spill over into Europe and Eurasia [65].

Unlike the Western Balkans, the republics on the Western perimeter of the Post-Soviet region have strong economic and political links with Russia and are considered part of Russia's "privileged interests" by President Dmitry Medvedev. Western influence and institutions, notably NATO, threaten Moscow's political power and security. Finally, regional organizations that foster collaboration and reduce conflict are lacking. BSEC was founded to promote regional cooperation. Fourth, the area has many historical grudges, boundary disputes, and "frozen wars." These disputes undermine regional security and collaboration [66].

Western policy has also changed internationally. Enlargement has been NATO and the EU's essential tool for eastward stability and security for 20 years. Since 2006, the EU focus has been the Lisbon Treaty ratification. Hence, Eastward expansion plans have received little support. The EU's principal policy tool for dealing with eastern peripheral nations, the Eastern Partnership, promotes commerce and soft power to strengthen connections [67].

Ukraine is challenging. Ukrainian policy changed after Viktor Yanukovich's 2010 victory. US and European strategies should build democratic institutions and promote civil society, including independent media. Georgia; Policy disputes between the US and Europe over Georgia, notably NATO membership, have decreased under President Obama. This may help the US and EU coordinate Georgia's strategy. The US and EU want Russia to leave Georgia. Abkhazia and South Ossetia are challenging challenges. US-EU coordination is needed here. Belarus: Europe's "last dictatorship" and poorest human rights record. Belarus has experienced subtle but significant changes in recent years. Russian policies imposed these reforms on Belarus. After the elections, the US and EU must reconsider Belarus's strategy. Yet, the US and EU must speak with one voice and coordinate policy. Moldova: The Pro-European Alliance for European

Integration (AEI) won the July 2009 parliamentary election, raising optimism that Moldova will choose a pro-European path. Turkey: The US and EU must engage Turkey more to promote stability and democracy in the Western Balkans and the EU's eastern neighbors. Turkey-US relations benefit the US and Europe. Turkey is becoming crucial to Europe's energy security and independence from Russia. Russia agreed to fund the Samsun-Ceyhan pipeline (SCP), which would link the Black Sea oil terminal in Samsun to the Mediterranean terminal in Ceyhan [68].

Conclusion

The paper examines Russo-American strategic relations, particularly armaments reduction. The fall of the USSR prompted the US to change its strategic weapons reduction strategy. The US was freed of a nuclear apocalypse once its greatest opponent disappeared. In the US weapons control community, Russian weakness is more dangerous than strength. Economic constraints prevent Russia from competing with the US in strategic weaponry. It cannot sustain the Soviet-inherited military apparatus. The Russian economy's shift from administrative to market was poorly executed, causing a catastrophe. As START II requires, Russia cannot sustain 3000-3500 strategic nuclear weapons.

Peace and stability in the Post-Cold War era led to American supremacy in those two decades, not Mutual Assured Destruction. The Soviet Union and the US's use of guaranteed annihilation to maintain world stability will continue.

Second, the balance of power politics has long fostered international peace. Henry Kissinger's Nixon administration's efforts to build a detente via a balanced global power structure fueled optimism that international stability had been permanently solved. The detente also relies on US-China ties and Japanese trust. This project comprised NATO and Soviet allies. The SALT Accord emphasized restrained military buildup. As long as statesmanship maintains equilibrium, the system can avert international war regardless of ideology.

Bismarck and Lansdowne, who had balanced the military and political strength of England, France, Germany, Russia, Austria, and Hungary during the late 19th century, were also responsible for the European system's congealment into the Triple Entente and Triple Alliance at the turn of the century.

Therefore, the issue arises of whether the US can now assure its own safety and international order stability. Second, diplomatic connections and conventional military commitments to NATO and East Asia and highlighting the American strategic posture (a flexible counter-force capacity against Soviet nuclear and conventional forces) would dissuade Soviet troops.

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